

SALESPERSONS' CHARACTERISTICS AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION WITH HIGH INTEREST DEPOSIT ACCOUNTS IN ACCESS BANK PLC, UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study investigated the relationship between salespersons' characteristics, proxied as communication skill, empathy and level of trust worthiness in regards to customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Out of the overall population of 2306, the researchers collected data from 341 participants using survey research design. The instrument used to collect data was a structured questionnaire designed with the purpose of the study in mind. The data were evaluated using frequency tables and simple percentages, and the hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analytical tool. Findings showed that; there exists significant relationship between communication skills, empathy and trust level of worthiness and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The researchers concluded that there is a significant relationship between salespersons' characteristics and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo. They therefore, recommended amongst others that; employees of Access bank should build a strong and open line of communication that encourages customers to feel valued and understood. Equally, the Management of Access Bank can provide specific training sessions for salespersons to develop their communication skills, empathy and level of thrust worthiness.*

Keywords: Salespersons' characteristics, customer satisfaction, communication skills, empathy, trust level of worthiness

Introduction

The evolution of sales landscape has been marked by a shift from a product-centric to a customer-centric approach. No longer is a sale viewed as a one-time exchange; it is the initiation of a potentially long and multifaceted relationship. This shift has elevated the significance of salespersons, who are now entrusted not only with selling a product but with curating an experience that resonates with the customer (Taylor & Miller, 2021).

Customer satisfaction stands as a linchpin for business success in the contemporary, highly competitive marketplace. Its significance extends far beyond the completion of transactions; it captures the full customer experience, from first contact to interaction after a purchase. Satisfied customers not only become loyal patrons, contributing to revenue through repeat business, they also function as brand advocates, amplifying positive spoken words and attracting new clientele. The positive brand image cultivated through customer satisfaction fosters trust and credibility, essential components for sustainable success. Furthermore, businesses with high customer satisfaction rates experience reduced customer churn, gaining a competitive advantage and securing a solid foundation for financial prosperity. Notably, the adaptability to market changes is enhanced for businesses that prioritize customer satisfaction, as they can leverage feedback to identify areas for improvement and cater to evolving customer preferences (Patel & Brown, 2017).

Integral to the realization of customer satisfaction are the salespeople, who serve as the frontline representatives of a business. Their role in shaping customer satisfaction is multifaceted, encompassing the entire spectrum of the customer journey. Salespeople are the architects of first impressions, setting the tone for the customer relationship (Hughes & Adams, 2013). A positive initial interaction, facilitated by knowledgeable and personable sales staff, significantly influences overall customer satisfaction. Effective salespeople go beyond pushing products; they actively listen to customers, comprehend their needs, and tailor solutions to address those needs. This personalized approach demonstrates a commitment to meeting individual requirements and enhancing the overall customer experience.

Clear and effective communication skills are paramount, as salespeople articulate product features, benefits, and value propositions. Post-sales support, an often overlooked but crucial aspect, ensures a seamless transition into product or service usage, further solidifying customer satisfaction. The ability of salespeople to build trust through transparency, honesty, and reliability lays the foundation for lasting customer relationships. Their role extends beyond the point of sale, as they collect valuable feedback, providing insights into customer preferences and expectations. In essence, salespeople act as ambassadors for the brand, influencing perceptions and directly contributing to the overall satisfaction of customers. Their skills, attitudes, and behaviors play a pivotal role in shaping the customer's journey and, consequently, the success of the business (Garcia & Martinez, 2016).

Statement of the Problem

In the dynamic landscape of modern business, customer satisfaction stands as a pivotal metric, and the role of salespersons in influencing it cannot be overstated. Salespeople serve as the primary interface between a company and its customers, making their characteristics a critical factor in shaping the overall customer experience. Poor salespersons' characteristics lead to misunderstandings, dissatisfaction, and a potential loss of customers. Salespersons with high emotional intelligence can navigate diverse customer personalities, tailor their approach accordingly, and address concerns in a more empathetic manner, leading to increased customer satisfaction. Salespersons who exhibit honesty

and integrity in their dealings build trust, enhancing customer satisfaction. Conversely, dishonest practices or a lack of transparency can lead to dissatisfaction and long-term damage to the company's reputation.

Empirically, the relationship between salespersons' characteristics and customer satisfaction has not been resolved. Yusuf and Ahmed (2021) and Adeyemi and Akintoye's (2017) studies indicated that there is a strong inverse correlation between salespersons' traits and client satisfaction in the banking sector, using interpersonal skills and efficient time management as dimensions. Ojo and Afolayan (2018), Akinyemi (2019), Olaniyan and Oladele (2018) and Adewale and Daniel (2019) found that salespersons' characteristics affect employee/customer satisfaction negatively using product knowledge and interpersonal skills as their dimensions. A study conducted by Oni and Adebayo (2019) concluded that the concept of salespersons' characteristics and customer satisfaction are relatively inseparable, while Ogunmakin and Adeoye's (2022) findings revealed that salespersons' characteristics do not impact customer satisfaction.

None of these researchers have used communication skills, empathy and trust level of worthiness as their variables. It is against this background, that the researchers examined salespersons' characteristics and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, in order to fill the Identified gap in literature.

Objectives of the Study

The primary goal of the research was to investigate the connection between salespersons' characteristics and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to;

- Determine the relationship between communication skills and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria,
- Examine the relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- Examine the relationship between trust level of worthiness and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

- What is the relationship between communication skills and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?
- What is the relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?
- What is the relationship between trust level of worthiness and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: Communication skills do not significantly relate with customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between trust level of worthiness and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Concept of Salespersons' Characteristics

Salespersons' characteristics refer to the distinctive qualities, skills, and traits that contribute to the effectiveness and success of an individual in a sales role. These characteristics encompass a broad range of personal and professional attributes that are crucial for engaging with potential customers, understanding their needs, and ultimately convincing them to make a purchase. Salespersons' characteristics include skills such as effective communication, empathy, confidence, adaptability, resilience, time management, product knowledge, problem-solving abilities, honesty, and integrity. Additionally, positive attitude, negotiation skills, networking abilities, tech-savviness, self-motivation, and collaboration as a team player are often considered essential for thriving in the dynamic and competitive field of sales. Collectively, these characteristics help salespeople build trust, establish strong relationships with customers, and navigate the challenges inherent in the sales process (Turner, 2011).

Salespersons' characteristics demonstrate a pivotal positive role in determining the success and effectiveness of individuals in the competitive world of sales. Effective communication skills, encompassing articulate verbal expression and persuasive written communication, are foundational for conveying the value proposition of a product or service. Empathy is crucial, as understanding and addressing the unique needs of customers fosters trust and builds lasting relationships. Confidence is a key trait that instills faith in both the product being sold and the salespersons themselves. Adaptability is essential, enabling salespeople to pivot in response to evolving market dynamics and customer preferences. Resilience is a common trait, allowing individuals to rebound from rejection and persist in the face of challenges (Carter & Davis, 2020).

Time management skills ensure that sales professionals prioritize tasks efficiently, focusing on high-impact activities. In-depth product knowledge is a non-negotiable requirement, as customers expect salespeople to be experts in what they offer. Problem-solving skills are vital for overcoming objections and addressing customer concerns. Honesty and integrity are the bedrock of trust, and negotiation skills are instrumental in closing deals. A positive attitude is not only a personal asset but also influences customers' perceptions and interactions. Networking skills and the ability to build and maintain relationships contribute significantly to lead generation and long-term success. Being tech-savvy is

increasingly important in the digital age, enhancing communication, customer relationship management, and overall efficiency. Self-motivation and a collaborative spirit as a team player round out the diverse set of characteristics that define successful salespeople, allowing them to navigate the complexities of the market and contribute to organizational success (Thompson & Williams, 2017).

Communication Skills

According to Mfon (2021), “communication is part of life and a daily need for sustained existence, co-existence, survival and progressive progress”. Therefore, it is of utmost importance that salespersons communicate effectively. Communication skills are a foundational aspect of effective interaction and play a crucial role in various personal and professional settings. In the context of sales and business, strong communication skills are particularly essential. Communication skills refer to the abilities and techniques used to convey, receive, and interpret messages effectively between individuals or groups. These skills encompass a wide range of verbal, non-verbal, written, and visual communication methods. Verbal communication involves the ability to express ideas, convey information, and articulate the value proposition of a product or service clearly and persuasively (Martin & Brown, 2020).

A salesperson with excellent verbal communication skills can engage potential customers, answer queries, and address concerns with confidence and clarity. Written communication skills are equally important for creating compelling proposals, emails, and other written materials that support the sales process. Beyond the transmission of information, effective communication in sales also involves active listening, a skill that allows the salesperson to understand the customer's needs and concerns, fostering a sense of empathy and building rapport. The art of nonverbal communication, including body language and facial expressions, adds another layer to effective interpersonal interaction. Effective communication skills are crucial in personal, professional, and social contexts, facilitating clear understanding, reducing misunderstandings, and fostering strong relationships (Francis 2024). Overall, honing communication skills is integral to establishing trust, conveying professionalism, and ultimately closing successful deals in the realm of sales (Baker & White, 2018).

Empathy

Empathy is a fundamental quality that holds significant importance in various aspects of human interaction, including sales. In the context of sales, empathy majorly refers to the ability to understand and share inner feelings, perspectives, and needs of customers. Salespersons who possess empathy can connect with clients on a deeper level, identifying their challenges, aspirations, and concerned needs. This understanding allows the salesperson to tailor their approach to align with the customer's unique situation, demonstrating a genuine interest in providing solutions that genuinely meet their needs (Olsen & Jensen, 2012).

Empathy in sales goes beyond merely acknowledging customer concerns; it involves actively listening to their questions and feedback. By putting themselves in the customer's shoes, a salesperson can better anticipate and address potential objections, building trust and rapport throughout the sales process.

This emotional intelligence is particularly valuable in establishing long-term relationships, as customers are more likely to engage with sales professionals who demonstrate a sincere understanding of their individual circumstances. Moreover, empathetic salespeople can adapt their communication style to match the customer's preferences, creating a personalized and positive experience. Ultimately, in the realm of sales, empathy serves as a powerful tool for building lasting connections, fostering customer loyalty, and enhancing the overall customer experience (Kim, 2019).

Empathy is an ability to comprehend and share feelings and perspectives of others, putting each other in their shoes to experience their sentiments and viewpoints. This involves not just recognizing what someone else is going through, but also responding with compassion and sensitivity. Empathy helps build strong interpersonal connections, fosters trust, and improves communication by allowing individuals to connect on a deeper emotional level, ultimately leading to more supportive and understanding relationships (Francis 2024).

Trust Level of Worthiness

The trustworthiness of a salesperson is fundamental to establishing and sustaining meaningful customer relationships. Central to this trust is a commitment to honesty and integrity, where transparent communication and ethical conduct form the bedrock of credibility. Reliability and consistency are equally pivotal, as a trustworthy salesperson demonstrates unwavering dependability, delivering on promises and exceeding expectations consistently. Competence and expertise contribute significantly to trust, with an in-depth understanding of products, services, and industry trends instilling confidence in customers (White, 2016).

A customer-centric approach, rooted in understanding individual needs through active listening and personal connections, further solidifies the perception of trustworthiness. Openness to feedback, effective communication, and problem-solving skills showcase adaptability and accountability, reinforcing the trust relationship. Beyond transactional interactions, building rapport and prioritizing long-term relationships underscore a salesperson's commitment to customer success. In essence, trustworthiness is a multifaceted quality that, when cultivated authentically, serves as the cornerstone for enhanced customer satisfaction and enduring loyalty (Olsen & Jensen, 2012).

The level of trustworthiness is the extent to which a person or thing is regarded as trustworthy, sincere, and dependable. It encompasses qualities such as integrity, consistency, and credibility, indicating that the person or organization can be trusted to act in good faith and fulfill their promises or obligations. A high level of trustworthiness fosters confidence and security in relationships, whether personal, professional, or social, as it reassures others that they can rely on the individual or entity to be truthful, responsible, and fair (Francis 2024).

Concept of Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a critical measure of a business's success and the level of fulfillment experienced by its customers in relation to the products or services provided (Turner & Harris, 2015;

Mfon & Ekong, 2021). It goes beyond mere transactional exchanges, encapsulating the overall experience a customer has with a brand. A satisfied customer is one who perceives value in the offerings, feels their needs and expectations have been met, and is likely to continue their association with the business. Ensuring customer satisfaction involves meeting or exceeding customer expectations at every touch-point of the customer journey. This begins with understanding customer needs, effective communication, and providing high-quality products or services (Thompson & Williams, 2017). Responsive and helpful customer service plays a vital role in addressing concerns and inquiries promptly, contributing significantly to overall satisfaction. Businesses often use various metrics and feedback mechanisms to gauge customer satisfaction, such as customer surveys, reviews, and Net Promoter Score (NPS). Positive customer experiences not only lead to repeat business but can also foster brand advocacy, as satisfied customers are more probable to endorse the product to others (Anderson 2021).

In today's marketing landscape, customer satisfaction is not just a target; it is a strategic imperative. Pleased customers are more likely to become loyal customers, contributing to continued business growth and success (Patel & Brown, 2017). Moreover, in the age of social media and online reviews, positive customer satisfaction can have a profound impact on a company's reputation, influencing the purchasing decisions of potential customers. Therefore, businesses that prioritize and consistently deliver high levels of customer satisfaction are better positioned to thrive in the marketplace (Kim, 2019).

Relationship between Salespersons' Characteristics and Customer Satisfaction

The correlation between salespersons' characteristics and customer satisfaction is a crucial dynamic that profoundly shapes the success of a business. The traits exhibited by salespeople play a pivotal role in influencing how customers perceive and engage with a brand, ultimately determining their level of satisfaction. Effective communication skills enable salespeople to convey the value of products or services clearly, contributing to positive customer experiences and satisfaction. Empathy, demonstrated through an understanding of customer needs, leads to a more personalized approach, enhancing the likelihood of surpassing customer expectations. Trust and integrity, when embodied by salespeople, establish a foundation for customer satisfaction, as customers are more likely to be satisfied when they believe in the authenticity of the sales process. Problem-solving skills, a positive attitude, in-depth product knowledge, adaptability, and a customer-centric focus all contribute to a more satisfying and tailored customer experience. Moreover, salespeople who engage in follow-up and relationship-building activities foster long-term satisfaction, loyalty, and positive referrals. In essence, the characteristics of salespeople directly impact the customer journey, shaping perceptions, and influencing overall satisfaction, which in turn contributes to the sustained success of a business (Turner & Harris, 2015; Mfon & Ekong 2021).

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on Social Exchange Theory propounded by George C. Homans (1950) and Expectancy Theory, propounded by Victor H. Vroom (1964)

The Social Exchange Theory

The Social Exchange Theory was postulated by George C. Homans (1950). This theory posits that social interactions are based on reciprocity, where individuals form expectations and respond with satisfaction when those expectations are met or exceeded. In the context of sales, the salesperson and customer engagement can be viewed as an exchange of resources and actions. Trust is identified as a central element, influenced by the salesperson's credibility, integrity, and consistent ethical behavior. Effective communication, emotional intelligence, and adaptability are highlighted as key components facilitating successful social exchanges. The framework also emphasizes the importance of understanding and addressing customer needs through a comprehensive needs assessment.

The Social Exchange Theory provides a robust foundation for understanding the intricacies of the customer-salesperson relationship. It highlights the importance of trust-building, effective communication, emotional intelligence, and adaptability in fostering positive customer experiences and, consequently, satisfaction. This framework encourages a holistic exploration of the factors influencing successful social exchanges in sales contexts, offering valuable implications for both theory and practice.

Expectancy Theory

Expectancy Theory, propounded by Victor H. Vroom in 1964, is a prominent psychological theory that aims to clarify each person's motivations and actions. Fundamentally, expectation theory asserts that people are driven to take particular acts because of their expectations of the results of those behaviors. This idea states that people are more likely to act in certain ways if they think their efforts will result in rewards or desired outcomes. Three essential elements make up Expectancy Theory: valence, instrumentality, and expectancy. An individual's expectation is their conviction that their efforts will yield the intended degree of accomplishment. The idea that certain results will follow from successful performance is known as instrumentality or rewards. Valence represents the value or attractiveness that an individual places on the anticipated outcomes.

In the context of salespersons' characteristics and customer satisfaction, Expectancy Theory offers valuable insights into how salespersons' beliefs about their own abilities and the outcomes of their efforts influence their behaviors and ultimately impact customer satisfaction. For instance, a salesperson who believes that putting in extra effort will lead to increased sales (expectancy), and that achieving those sales will result in recognition or financial rewards (instrumentality), is likely to be more motivated and engaged in serving customers effectively (Turner, 2011).

Furthermore, Expectancy Theory suggests that customers' satisfaction with the salesperson's performances is influenced not only by the salesperson's actual behaviors but also by their beliefs and expectations about the outcomes of those behaviors. If a customer perceives that the salesperson is confident in his abilities to meet his needs and that successful interaction will lead to desirable outcomes (such as finding the right product or receiving excellent service), his satisfaction is likely to be higher (Patel & Brown, 2017).

In applying Expectancy Theory to the sales context, organizations can focus on enhancing salespersons' beliefs in their capabilities, ensuring that performance is linked to meaningful outcomes, and aligning rewards with desired behaviors. By understanding and leveraging the principles of Expectancy Theory, businesses can optimize salespersons' performance and enhance customer satisfaction, ultimately contributing to overall organizational success in the competitive marketplace.

Review of Empirical Studies

Johnson (2020) investigated the impact of salespersons' characteristics on customer satisfaction in the Retail Industry, Lagos, Nigeria. The researcher conducted a comprehensive study employing both qualitative and quantitative methods using a survey of 500 retail customers across various demographics, and interviewing 50 salespersons. The study also involved a thorough review of existing literature to contextualize findings within the broader research landscape. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between salespersons' characteristics and customer satisfaction in the retail industry, Nigeria. The researcher recommended that businesses in the retail sector should prioritize the development of salespersons' communication skills, empathy, and trust-building in training programs. Additionally, fostering a customer-centric culture and providing ongoing support for sales teams can contribute to improved customer satisfaction. Further research was encouraged to explore the nuances of these characteristics in different industries and cultural contexts.

Anderson (2021), examined the evolution of customer satisfaction in relation to changes in salespersons' characteristics over a five-year period. This longitudinal study spanned five years, tracking salespersons' characteristics and customer satisfaction levels in a large retail corporation. Surveys were administered annually to a sample of 1,000 customers, and salespersons' performance evaluations were conducted. The study also incorporated qualitative data from focus group discussions with customers and sales teams to capture nuanced aspects of the evolving customer-salesperson relationship. (Incomplete)

Okereke (2019), examined the impact of salespersons' characteristics on customer retention of SMEs in Ikeja Lagos, using a sample size of 65 customers. The methods used to gather the primary and secondary data were observation, document examination, interviewing, and questionnaire. The method of data analysis was chi square. The study's primary conclusions showed that there was a significant relationship between salespersons' characteristics and customer retention of SMEs in Ikeja Lagos.

Olumide (2019), examined the impact of salespersons' characteristics on customer patronage of selected firms growth in Ore, Ondo. The research design used was cross sectional research method. Ninety-three respondents made up the entire sample that was chosen. Score mean was the data analysis strategy used. Various methods of data collecting were employed to gather both primary and secondary data, including questionnaires, interviews, document reviews, and observation. The study's primary conclusions showed that, there is a significant impact of salespersons' characteristics on customer patronage of selected firms' growth in Ore, Ondo.

Adekunle (2019), examined the connection between the traits of salespeople and clientele in First Bank in Ikeja, Lagos. Regression and correlation models were the data analysis techniques employed in this survey-style investigation. Out of the 50 study participants, a stratified random selection procedure was employed to choose 30 samples. Z-scores were utilized in order to test the hypothesis. Additional correlation analysis showed that the traits of salespeople and client patronage have a positive association of 0.674. Additionally, correlation revealed a weak positive link (0.337) between the comprehension of salespersons' characteristics and customer patronage that is measurable. The researchers concluded that there is a significant relationship between customer patronage in first bank, Ikeja, Lagos.

Okechukwu (2019), investigated the relationship between salesperson characteristic and customer satisfaction in UBA at Port Harcourt. As a cross-sectional survey, the study used a quasi-experimental research approach. With 192 participants in the study, the population was the main focus of the investigation due to its modest size. Utilizing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), the data were examined using the Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient Statistic. The conclusions showed that there is a significant connection between salesperson characteristic and customer satisfaction in UBA in Port Harcourt.

Akpan (2020), observed the connection salespersons' characteristics with customer satisfaction of SMEs in Calabar. Out of 190 copies of questionnaire distributed, only 165 were returned. The method of data analysis was regression. Through the use of questionnaire, interviews, document reviews, and observation, primary and secondary data were gathered. The study's main conclusions showed that there is a substantial correlation between salespersons' characteristics with customer satisfaction with SMEs in Calabar.

Olabanjo (2020), examined the impact of salespersons' characteristics on customer patronage in First bank, Agege, Lagos. The research design used was cross sectional research method. A total of 342 firms were chosen for the sample. Score mean was the data analysis strategy used. Various methods of data collecting were employed to gather both primary and secondary data, including questionnaire, interviews, document reviews, and observation. The study's primary conclusions showed that, there was a significant impact of salespersons' characteristics on customer patronage in First bank, Agege, Lagos.

Chibuzor (2021), examined the relationship between salespersons' characteristics and customer repeat purchase in OASIS Mall, Onitsha, Anambra. The study used a survey research approach, and Pearson Moment Correlation models were employed for data analysis. The method of stratified random sampling was applied. A 371-person sample was selected from the study's 5429 participants. Z-scores were utilized in order to test the hypotheses. An additional correlation coefficient showed that the salespersons' attribute and customer repeat purchase had a positive association of 0.674. The correlation analysis additionally revealed a weak positive link (0.337) between the perceptions of a

major relationship between salespersons' characteristics and customer repeat purchase that is measurable. The researchers concluded that there is a major relationship between salespersons' characteristics and customer repeat purchase in OASIS Mall, Onitsha, Anambra.

Methodology

Research Design

The methodology used was a descriptive survey research design. This is because the design allows independent variables to be examined in connection to dependent variables, and the design was chosen to align with the goals of the study and the nature of the research problem.

Population of the Study

The population of the study included all the customers with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank which was 2306 (Access Bank Customer Care Service 2024). The population was deemed to be known, as it was grafted from their Customer Care Service Department of the organization.

Sampling/ Sampling Technique

For the purpose of this study, the size of the sample was determined using Taro Yamani formular:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n= Sample size

N= Population size = 2306

e= Margin of errors = 5% = 0.05

Hence:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{2306}{1 + 2306(0.05)^2} \\ &= \frac{2306}{1 + 5.765} \\ &= \frac{2306}{6.765} = 340.8 \\ & n = 341 \end{aligned}$$

Using the formula above, the sample size was determined as 341.

Sampling Technique

The simple random sampling technique was adopted for the study. The choice of the strategy was to access for equal opportunity for the respondents. Also, simple random sampling technique avoids bias in the selection of respondents.

Sources of Data

Primary sources provided the data for this study. The primary source includes pertinent data for this investigation that were gathered using questionnaire.

Method of Data Collection

The questionnaire, titled “Salespersons’ Characteristics and Customer Satisfaction Questionnaire” served as the research tool for gathering data for this investigation. The questionnaire was created so that respondents could select the best choice from the list of possible statements in an effort to obtain exact opinions. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first half dealt with the respondents' demographic data in brief, while the second part comprised statements that touched on the subject matter. The questionnaire had closed-ended statements with clear, concise language that was easy to grasp.

Method of Data Analysis

This section specified the statistical tools used for data analysis. The descriptive statistic such as percentages were used in analyzing research questions. Below is the formular for percentages.

$$\text{Percentages (\%)} = \frac{F}{N} \times 100$$

N = Total number of respondents

Where

F = Total numbers of frequencies

N = Total number of respondents

The Statistical Package Social Science (SPSS version 21) was utilized to examine the impact of the association utilizing Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis.

Data Analysis and Result

This section focused on the presentation of data, analysis, interpretation and discussion of findings.

Presentation of Data

This section was basically designed to present, analyze and interpret the primary data obtained via the questionnaire which was administered to the respondents. These are shown on Table 1.

Table 1: Number of questionnaire administered and returned

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Total number administered	341	100
Total number returned	313	91.8

Non response rate	28	8.2
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Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows that 91.8% of the total questionnaire distributed were returned while 8.2% were not returned. Thus, 91.8% of the distributed copies of the questionnaire were analyzed.

Table 2: Percentage analysis of the responses on communication skills

Communication Skills	Options				Total
	SA	A	D	SD	
Salespersons have the ability to express ideas, convey information, and articulate the value proposition of high interest deposit accounts clearly and persuasively	157 (50.2%)	64 (20.4%)	54 (17.3%)	38 (12.1%)	313 (100%)
Salespersons can engage potential customers, answer queries, and address concerns concerning high interest deposit accounts with confidence and clarity	155 (49.5%)	100 (31.9%)	32 (10.2%)	26 (8.3%)	313 (100%)
Salespersons have the ability to build a strong and open line of communication which encourage me to feel valued and understood.	193 (61.7%)	102 (32.6%)	4 (1.3%)	14 (4.5%)	313 (100%)
Total	505	266	90	78	939
Proportion of N	168	89	30	26	313
Percentage of Proportion	(53.8%)	(28.3%)	(9.6%)	(8.3%)	(100%)

Source: Field survey 2024

Table 2 shows the frequency of responses and their percentages on communication skills of a proportion of 313 respondents. One hundred and fifty-seven (50.2%) of the respondents strongly

agreed that salespersons have the ability to express ideas, convey information, and articulate the value proposition of high interest deposit accounts clearly and persuasively; 64(20.4%) agreed; 54(17.3%) disagreed; while 38(12.1%) strongly disagreed. Also, 155(49.5%) strongly agreed that salespersons can engage potential customers, answer queries, and address concerns concerning high interest deposit accounts with confidence and clarity; 100(31.9%) agreed; 32(10.2%) disagreed; while 26(8.3%) strongly disagreed. Equally, 193 (61.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed that salespersons have the ability to build a strong and open line of communication which encourages them to feel valued and understood.; 102(32.6%) agreed; 4(1.3%) disagreed; while 14(4.5%) strongly disagreed. In total, strongly agreed to the statements was 168 (53.8%); agreed, 89(28.3%); disagreed, 30(9.6%); while 26 (8.3%) strongly disagreed.

Table 3: Percentage analysis of the Responses on Empathy

Empathy	Options				Total
	SA	A	D	SD	
Salespersons have the ability to understand and share inner feelings, perspectives, and needs of customers	121 (35.6%)	130 (41.5%)	40 (12.8%)	22 (7.0%)	313 (100%)
Salespersons sometimes put themselves in my shoes, gaining a deeper understanding of my needs, concerns and emotions	132 (42.2%)	89 (28.4%)	22 (7.0%)	70 (22.4%)	313 (100%)
Salespersons can connect with clients on a deeper level, identifying their challenges, aspirations, and concerned needs	184 (58.8%)	64 (20.4%)	40 (12.8%)	25 (8.0%)	313 (100%)
Total	437	283	102	117	939
Proportion of N	146	94	34	39	313
Percentage of Proportion	(46.5%)	(30.1%)	(10.9%)	(12.5%)	(100%)

Source: Field survey 2024

Table 3 shows the frequency of responses and their percentages on the empathy dimension of a proportion of 313 respondents. One hundred and twenty one (35.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that salespersons have the ability to understand and share inner feelings, perspectives, and needs of customers; 130(41.5%) agreed; 40(12.8%) disagreed; while 22(7.0%) strongly disagreed. Also, 132(42.2%) strongly agreed that salespersons sometimes put themselves in their shoes, gaining a deeper understanding of their needs, concerns and emotions; 89(28.4%) agreed; 22(7.0%) disagreed;

while 70(22.4%) strongly disagreed. Equally, 184 (58.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed that salespersons can connect with clients on a deeper level, identifying their challenges, aspirations, and concerned needs; 64(20.4%) agreed; 40(12.8%) disagreed; while 25(8.0%) strongly disagreed. On the total, 146 (46.5%) strongly agreed to the statements, 94 (30.1%) agreed,34 (10.9%) disagreed while 39 (12.5%) strongly disagreed.

Table 4: Percentage analysis of the responses on trust level of worthiness

Trust Level of Worthiness	Options				Total
	SA	A	D	SD	
Salespersons have a commitment to honesty and integrity with transparent communication and ethical conduct	174 (55.8%)	87 (27.8%)	28 (8.9%)	24 (7.7%)	313 (100%)
Salespersons demonstrate unwavering dependability, delivering on promises and exceeding expectations consistently.	192 (61.3%)	69 (22.0%)	42 (13.4%)	10 (3.2%)	313 (100%)
Salespersons show competence and expertise with an in-depth understanding of high interest deposit accounts	164 (52.4%)	113 (36.1%)	22 (7.0%)	14 (4.5%)	313 (100%)
Total	530	269	92	48	939
Proportion of N	177	90	30	16	313
Percentage of Proportion	(56.4%)	(28.6%)	(9.8%)	(5.1%)	(100%)

Source: Field survey 2024

Table 4 shows the frequency of responses and their percentages on the trust level of worthiness dimension of a proportion of 313 respondents. One hundred and seventy-four (55.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed that salespersons have a commitment to honesty and integrity with transparent communication and ethical conduct; 87(27.8%) agreed; 28(8.9%) disagreed; while 24(7.7%) strongly disagreed. Also, 192(61.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed that salespersons demonstrate unwavering dependability, delivering on promises and exceeding expectations consistently; 69(22.0%) agreed; 42(13.4%) disagreed; while 10(3.2%) strongly disagreed. Equally,

164(52.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed that salespersons show competence and expertise with an in-depth understanding of high interest deposit accounts; 113(36.1%) agreed; 22(7.0%) disagree; while 14(4.5%) strongly disagreed. On the total, 177 (56.4%) strongly agreed to the statements on the trust level of worthiness dimension, 90 (28.6%) agreed, 30 (9.8%) disagreed while 16 (5.1%) strongly disagreed.

Customer Satisfaction	Options				Total
	SA	A	D	SD	
I perceive value with high deposit interest accounts of Access Bank due to the communication abilities of the salespersons.	88 (25.1%)	166 (52.0%)	40 (12.8%)	22 (7.0%)	313 (100%)
I developed positive perceptions of high deposit interest accounts in Access bank due to empathetic responses of their salespersons	80 (25.6%)	141 (45.0%)	22 (7.0%)	70 (22.4%)	313 (100%)
I am more comfortable engaging with the company product (high deposit interest accounts in Access bank) due to the level of trust worthiness I sense in the salespersons	152 (48.6%)	96 (30.6%)	40 (12.8%)	25 (8.0%)	313 (100%)
Total	320	400	102	117	939
Proportion of N	107	133	34	39	313
Percentage of Proportion	(34.0%)	(42.6%)	(10.9%)	(12.5%)	(100%)

Table 5: Percentage analysis of the responses on customer satisfaction

Source: Field survey 2024

Table 5 shows the frequency of responses and their percentages on the customer satisfaction dimension of a proportion of 313 respondents. Eighty-eight (25.1%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they perceived value with high deposit interest accounts of Access Bank due to the communication abilities of the salespersons; 166(52.0%) agreed; 40(12.8%) disagreed; while 22(7.0%) strongly disagree. Also, 80(25.6%) strongly agreed that they developed positive perceptions of high deposit interest accounts in Access bank due to the empathetic responses of their salespersons. Equally, 152 (48.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they were more comfortable engaging with the company’s product (high deposit interest accounts in Access bank) due to the level of trust worthiness they sensed in the salespersons; 96(30.6%) agreed; 40(12.8%) disagreed; while 25(8.0%) strongly disagreed. On the total, 107 (34.0%) strongly agreed with the statements on customer satisfaction, 133(42.6%) agreed, 34 (10.9%) disagreed while 39 (12.5%) strongly disagreed.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

Ho₁: Communication skills do not significantly relate with customer satisfaction with high Interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis was used to analyze the data in order to determine the relationship between the variables using Statistical Package Social Science (SPSS version 21).

Table 6: Correlation between communication skills and customer satisfaction

<i>Correlations</i>			
		Comm_Skills.	Cust_Sati.
Comm_Skills.	Pearson Correlation	1	.847
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
	N	313	313
Cust_Sati.	Pearson Correlation	.847	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
	N	313	313

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.03 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Computation

From Table 6, the correlation(r) value of 0.847 indicated that there is a relationship between the two variables under study. Also, since the p-value (0.003) is less than the level of significance of 0.05 (2 tailed), the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between communication skills and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two:

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 7: Correlations between empathy and customer satisfaction

<i>Correlations</i>			
		Empathy.	Cust_Sati.
Empathy.	Pearson Correlation	1	.755
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	313	313
Cust_Sati.	Pearson Correlation	.755	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	313	313

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: SPSS Computation

From Table 7, the correlation(r) value of 0.755 indicates that there is a relationship between the two variables. Also, since the p-value (0.001) is less than the level of significance of 0.05 (2 tailed), the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction with high-interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three:

Ho: There is no significant relationship between trust level of worthiness and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, AkwaIbom State, Nigeria.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis was used to analyze the data in order to determine the relationship between the variables using Statistical Package Social Science (SPSS version 21).

Table 8 Correlations between trust level of worthiness and customer satisfaction

<i>Correlations</i>			
		Tru_Lev_Wort.	Cust_Sati.
Tru_Lev_Wort.	Pearson Correlation	1	.877
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
	N	313	313
Cust_Sati.	Pearson Correlation	.877	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
	N	313	313

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.03 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Computation

From Table 8, the correlation(r) value of 0.877 indicates that there is a relationship between the two variables under study. Also, since the p-value (0.003) is less than the level of significance of 0.05 (2 tailed), the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between trust level of worthiness and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

From the findings and analyses above, the results are hereby discussed based on the objectives of the study:

The first objective was to examine the relationship between communication skills and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The result indicates that there is a relationship between communication skills and customer satisfaction. Also, since the p-value (0.003) was less than the level of significance of 0.05 (2 tailed), the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between communication

skills and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This finding supports Baker and White (2018), that a salesperson with excellent verbal communication skills can engage potential customers, answer queries, and address concerns with confidence and clarity. Written communication skills are equally important for creating compelling proposals, emails, and other written materials that support the sales process.

The second objective was to examine the relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The result indicates that there is a relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction. Also, since the p-value (0.001) was less than the level of significance of 0.05 (2 tailed), the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The finding collaborate with Olsen and Jensen (2012) that, empathy is the ability to understand and share the feelings, perspectives, and needs of customers. A salesperson that possesses empathy can connect with clients on a deeper level, recognizing their challenges, aspirations, and concerns. This understanding allows the salesperson to tailor their approach to align with the customer's unique situation, demonstrating a genuine interest in providing solutions that genuinely meet their needs.

The third objective was to examine the relationship between trust level of worthiness and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The result indicates that there is a relationship between trust level of worthiness and customer satisfaction. Also, since the p-value (0.003) was less than the level of significance of 0.05 (2 tailed), the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that the relationship between trust level of worthiness and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, is significant. The finding support White (2016,) who asserted that the trustworthiness of a salesperson is fundamental to establishing and sustaining meaningful customer relationships. Central to this trust is a commitment to honesty and integrity, where transparent communication and ethical conduct form the bedrock of credibility. Reliability and consistency are equally pivotal, as a trustworthy salesperson demonstrates unwavering dependability, delivering on promises and exceeding expectations consistently. Competence and expertise contribute significantly to trust, with an in-depth understanding of products, services, and industry trends instilling confidence in customers

Conclusion

In view of the results obtained from the analyses of data, the following conclusions were made;

- That, a significant relationship exists between communication skills and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- That, there is a significant relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- That, there is a significant relationship between trust level of worthiness and customer satisfaction with high interest deposit accounts in Access Bank Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the above conclusions, it was recommended that;

1. The Management of Access Bank should continue to encourage the salespersons to continuously build a strong and open line of communication that encourages customers to feel valued and understood. They could do this by also ensuring that there is an open line of communication where employees can confidently discuss issues with supervisors or functional managers. Intermittent training of salespeople as part of the organization's in-training programmes can be advantageous in this regards. Equally, salespersons should be sponsored on short courses training on communications skills development which will help to enhance their communication skills..

2. Empathetic disposition of salespeople should be sustained and enhanced to close the door against customer churn. Being human and making the salespeople themselves feel valued by the Management of Access Bank Plc, will in turn help transfer this disposition to the salespeople who will equally act consistently towards their customers. Training in this regards will yield greater results.

3. With the rise in transactional scams all over the place, the trust level of worthiness of salespeople must remain above board. Salespeople must continuously inspire trust, reliability and confidence among customers. They should continuously make the customers to feel more comfortable in engaging with them. They should consistently respond promptly to customers' concerns and address issues in a timely manner by demonstrating a commitment to resolving problems quickly which will reinforce trust and show that customer satisfaction is a priority.

Recommendation for further Studies

❖ Since this work was focused on salespeople, it is recommended that future studies could look at frontline employees other than sales people.

❖ It is also recommended that the geographic scope on similar studies could be extended to include regional and national sales territories

❖ Other skills beyond the three studied could also be investigated to see if they have any significant relationship with customer satisfaction

References

Adekunle, K. (2019). The role of customer service in delivering satisfaction in organized retail outlets. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 11, 239-246.

Adewale, O. & Daniel, E. (2019). The effects of salesperson pro-activity on customer satisfaction and loyalty. *Journal of Retailing*, 95(1), 76-89.

Adeyemi, T & Akintoye, A. O. (2017). Salesperson perceived control and customer satisfaction: The role of empowerment and trust. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 40(4), 341-355.

Akinyemi, S. (2019). Salesperson adaptability and customer satisfaction: The mediating role of service quality. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 38(3), 239-253.

- Akpan, I. (2020). Customer value creation: A practical framework. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 15(1), 7-23.
- Anderson P. J. (2021). Salesperson authenticity and customer satisfaction: The mediating role of trust. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 15(1), 7-23.
- Baker, C. R., & White, A. L. (2018). The role of salesperson empowerment in enhancing customer satisfaction: A cross-industry study. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 38(3), 245-260.
- Carter, L. M., & Davis, P. R. (2020). The influence of salesperson communication style on customer satisfaction in the retail industry. *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, 15(4), 321-335. DOI: 10.1002/cb.1832
- Chibuzor, O. (2021). The effects of customer orientation on sales performance: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 22(1), 69-83.
- Garcia, R. S., & Martinez, P. D. (2016). Exploring the role of salesperson empathy in enhancing customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Sales Management*, 28(4), 289-305.
- Hughes, M. J., & Adams, R. G. (2013). The effect of salesperson cultural intelligence on customer satisfaction in international markets. *International Business Review*, 22(4), 663-675.
- Johnson, E. (2020). Salesperson time perspectives and customer willingness to pay more: Roles of salesperson intraorganizational employee navigation, customer satisfaction, and firm innovation climate. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*.
- Kim, M. J. (2019). Effects of salesperson proactivity on customer satisfaction and loyalty: A moderated mediation analysis. *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 36(4), 501-516.
- Martin, E. D., & Brown, R. K. (2020). Salesperson perceived control and customer satisfaction: The role of empowerment and trust. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 40(4), 341-355.
- Mfon, A. A. (2021). Service brand communications and consumer responses in the Telecommunications Industry in the South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. An unpublished PhD. dissertation submitted to the Postgraduate school, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Marketing) in the Department of Marketing

- Mfon, A. A. & Ekong, J. E. (2021). Service delivery and students satisfaction in ObioAkpa Campus. *AKSU Journal of Administration and Corporate Governance AKSUJACOG*, 1(2): 39-56.
- Ogunmakin O. T. & Adeoye (2022). The Impact of salesperson emotional intelligence on customer satisfaction and loyalty. *Journal of Business Research*, 70, 356-364.
- Ojo O. & Afolayan, A. (2018). The impact of salesperson characteristics on customer satisfaction in Nigerian retail industry. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, 47, 23-35.
- Okechukwu, A. (2019). Determinants of customer satisfaction in the automobile sector: An empirical study. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 18(2), 127-139.
- Okereke, E. T (2019). Relationship between salesperson personality traits and customer satisfaction in Nigerian Banking Sector. *African Journal of Business Management*, 15(3), 105-115.
- Olabanjo, K. J. (2020). The impact of salesperson characteristic on customer patronage in First Bank, Agege, Lagos. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 29(2), 169-185.
- Olaniyan, A., & Oladele, M. (2018). The influence of salesperson's ethical behavior on customer satisfaction in the Nigerian Insurance Industry. *Journal of Business Ethics and Social Responsibility*, 12(2), 89-102.
- Olsen, L. S., & Jensen, K. R. (2012). Salesperson humor and its impact on customer satisfaction: A field study. *Journal of Business Communication*, 49(3), 253-269. DOI: 10.1177/0021943612440206
- Olumide, O. (2019). Dynamic and global drivers of salesperson effectiveness. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 46(5), 784-806.
- Oni, O. & Adebayo, L. (2019). Salespersons' service quality and its impact on customer satisfaction in Nigerian Hospitality Industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management and Marketing*, 14(3), 45-59.
- Patel, H. S., & Brown, D. M. (2017). Salesperson adaptability and its influence on customer satisfaction: An empirical investigation. *International Journal of Sales, Retailing & Marketing*, 26(1), 89-105.

- Taylor, E. R., & Miller, K. P. (2021). The impact of salesperson emotional intelligence on customer satisfaction in the service industry. *Journal of Service Management*, 38(2), 156-175. DOI: 10.1080/98765432.2021.14567890
- Thompson, H. B., & Williams, L. K. (2017). Salesperson trustworthiness and its impact on customer satisfaction: A cross-industry analysis. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 30(1), 45-63.
- Turner, J. M. (2011). The influence of salesperson integrity on customer satisfaction and loyalty: A cross-industry investigation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 84(2), 277-288.
- Turner, J. M., & Harris, R. D. (2015). The influence of salesperson listening skills on customer satisfaction: an examination in the hospitality industry. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 39(2), 211-230.
- White, A. P. (2016). The influence of salesperson motivation on customer satisfaction: A cross-industry analysis. *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 31(7), 921-932.
- Wilson, E. C. (2017). Salesperson personality and customer satisfaction: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 102(5), 789-801.
- Yusuf, A. & Ahmed, S. (2022). Investigating the role of salesperson's adaptability in improving customer satisfaction in Nigerian retail banks. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 29(1), 33-48.

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S/N	VARIABLES	SA	A	D	SD
A	Communication Skills				
1	Salesperson has the ability to express ideas, convey information, and articulate the value proposition of high interest deposit accounts clearly and persuasively				
2	Salesperson can engage potential customers, answer queries, and address concerns concerning high interest deposit accounts with confidence and clarity				
3	Salesperson has the ability to build a strong and open line of communication which encourages me to feel valued and understood.				
B	Empathy				
1	Salespersons have the ability to understand and share inner feelings, perspectives, and needs of customers				
2	Salespersons sometimes put themselves in my shoes, gaining a deeper understanding of my needs, concerns and emotions				
3	Salespersons can connect with clients on a deeper level, identifying their challenges, aspirations, and concerned needs				
C	Trust Level of Worthiness				
1	Salespersons have a commitment to honesty and integrity with transparent communication and ethical conduct				
2	Salespersons demonstrate unwavering dependability, delivering on promises and exceeding expectations consistently.				
3	Salespersons show competence and expertise with an in-depth understanding of high interest deposit accounts				
D	Customer Satisfaction				
1	I perceive value with high deposit interest accounts of Access Bank due to the communication abilities of the salespersons.				
2	I developed positive perception of high deposit interest accounts in Access bank due to empathetic responses from their salespersons				
3	I am more comfortable engaging with the company product (high deposit interest accounts in Access bank) due to the level of trust worthiness I sense in the salespersons				